

Homeland another perspective

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Abstract: In a dialogue of Plato, a text that has generated many imaginative approaches and detaching from those, I identify numerous elements specific to the Proto-Indo-European culture, which allow me to formulate the hypothesis that the subject in question is represented by the ancient civilization itself. Based on this assumption, I discover a lot of new information that needs to be studied and especially about what we now call Homeland. Even if the text is so far from the scientific rigor of today, the relevant cultural elements that are included, point to a much earlier discovery - 360 B.C. of three social functions, for example, or confirm many others contemporary discoveries about the ancient civilization.

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I. On the text in question

1. Plato (429?-347 BC), an Athenian citizen of high status, was aware of how philosophy should be conceived and what is its purpose and ambitions. He has transformed so many topics that he has addressed that we can say philosophy, as a matter of rigorous and systematic examination of social, ethical, political, metaphysical and epistemological issues, belongs to him. Few other authors in the history of Western philosophy approach in depth and in the subject matter, perhaps only Aristotle, Aquinas or Kant could have the same rank. I approach a specific philosophical perspective, because it allows, in addition to the detailed observation of the current archaeological and linguistic discoveries, to formulate conclusions that may be freer than the academic rigor specific to a particular scientific field, noting that neither of them has formulated unsurprising hypotheses. Plato's dialogues do not attempt to create a fictional world for the purposes of telling a story, as many literary dramas do; nor do they invoke an earlier mythical realm, like the creations of the great Greek tragedians Aeschylus, Sophocles, and Euripides. Dialogues are philosophical

discussions and "debates" would be a more appropriate word (Kraut 2017).

2. Some people are perfectly capable of disinterested thinking, they are moved by a need or a desire to understand the world around them, its nature and their society. To achieve that end, they proceed by intellectual means, exactly as a philosopher, or a scientist, can and would do (Lévi-Strauss 1978.5). They archive their knowledge and by joining them with an extraordinary, something that attracts attention, create the myth. The ancient Greeks seem to have been persons with common sense and their discourse had the capacity to retain truthful information on the subject in question. I will begin by presenting the text by telling you that, although it is well known he generated numerous polemics, stirring up the imaginary at extreme. I have approached a completely different perspective on it. Then I didn't do this approach using my own imagination, but I tried to rely on the issues that I observed as being current and carried in the academic environment.

3. Therefore when he states that, the man who likes myths is a some kind of philosopher Aristotle admits that who likes myths actually likes wisdom (Aristotle Book (A) 2.). This is because the myth contains a part of the truth, one codified, useful and possible to transmit.

4. Although I am aware that just remembering the title of the text, from the very beginning it will make you stop reading suddenly, because I will arouse a huge feeling of mistrust, but I am obliged to do that without unnecessarily prolonging my text. The dialogue I refer to is Plato, Timaeus - Critias, which is the source of the myth of Atlantis. The actual date of composition of Timaeus and Critias is probably around 360 bc, but there is nothing to fix that with any great precision (Plato 2008.XIV). I used the Robin Waterfield's translation, Oxford University Press 2008.

II. The road I don't want to go

5. Although it is not important in Plato's work, the story of Atlantis had a considerable impact on the literature. For many centuries the myth of the lost Atlantis served as a lure for explorers, geographers, archeologists, and nationalists to search for its supposed site (Mohr 2010:329). The works of several Renaissance writers have appeared, such as Francis Bacon in *New Atlantis* and Thomas More in *Utopia*. The first one imagines the enlarging of the bounds of Human Empire, to the effecting of all things possible (Bacon 99) and the second talk about internal pasaport (More 72), public hospitals (id. 68) dining halls (id.69), religion (id.81) and more.

6. On the other hand, later amateur scholars misinterpreted Plato's narrative, such as Ignatius L. Donnelly's *Atlantis: The Antediluvian World*. Plato's vague indications of the timing of events - well over 9,000 years before his time and the supposed location of Atlantis - "beyond Hercules' pillars" - have led to many pseudo-scientific speculations. Even if he talks about, the Aryan Colonies from Atlantis, he is far from making tangible arguments. (DONNELLY Part V The

Colonies Of Atlantis).

7. There have been numerous attempts to identify Atlantis "island" in different parts of the world. An new identification was made for the bottom of the Black Sea and it also seems to be based on landmarks without consistent support (2004). The authors show that, until around 5500 BC the Black Sea was a smaller lake, and the breaking Bosphorus sill led to a flood commonly referred to as Noah's Flood. Although heavily attacked, just recently this theory has gained weird support from new studies.

The authors proposed that the Atlantis was an early Neolithic settlement at the former shoreline of that lake (Sigfried 2004). When comparing the writing from Atlantis with the writing from Vincza does not take into account the place where this writing was discovered, and when discussing about the Tocharians does not follow their DNA link. However, we agree that the whole of Atlantis could not be an island (id.) and we still believe that it was bordering on an area inhabited by old Russian-speaking populations (lat. rus "Country, farm"). Then it also seems true that, the Greek culture known today is derived from tribes of the north invading the peninsula 1950 BC coming from Europe, and it is not identical with the Greek culture referred to in the Atlantis saga (id.).

8. In another perspective, Indo-European homelands have been identified in India, Pakistan, the Himalayas, the Altai Mountains, Kazakhstan, Russia, Ukraine, the Balkans, Turkey, Armenia, the North Caucasus, Syria/Lebanon, Germany, Scandinavia, the North Pole, and old hypothetical Atlantis (Anthony 2007:83) All the identifications were based on nationalist issues, although we had to look at a territory where the spoken languages are very different and have an unidentified formation with certainty.

9. The Italian literary scholar Giuseppe Bartoli came to the conclusion agreed upon by most contemporary scholars: that the Atlantis fable was simply that, a convenient fiction invented out of more or less whole cloth by Plato as a way of criticizing the Athens of his own day (Mohr 2010:330). Then it seems that the story itself would have been a favored dialogue, and not scientific, because Critias himself was an Athenian for whom, some have suggested, it have been Plato's uncle or perhaps his great-grandfather (Feder 2010.30).

10. It was then stated that, Proto-Indo-European probably evolved out of the languages spoken by hunter-fishing communities in the Pontic-Caspian region (Mallory 1989.262). These it certainly belongs to the sphere of speculation, the location of the Indo-European homeland in the arid steppe environment of the Pontic-Caspian region , where flooding could be more beneficial, not a catastrophe. (Penney 2004.334) Cannabis smoking was introduced into the Danube Valley by Yamnaya immigrants (Russia). (3000 BC), so the wheel of history made a different sense (Anthony 2007.362).

11. I am not at all interested in these aspects, even though the former are fascinating for relaxing reading, and the latter can create confusing. A language necessarily implies the existence of a society, a community of speech and culture, and a proto-language necessarily implies a "proto-culture", that is, the culture of the users of proto-language (Watkins 1995.7), The text contains many cultural elements that are currently considered to belong to Proto-Indo-Europeans.

III. Specific elements of The Proto-Indo-European culture and their correspondence in the text

12. Returning to our text, I identify the relevant parts and their curious correspondence with specific Proto-Indo-European cultural elements. In the final part, I formulate certain hypotheses, without having by far the claims of completeness, but on the contrary, being aware that I have documented a summary and made some suggestions, not establishing any demonstration.

13. As this quick exploration shows, the recent article in Science on the origin, expansion of the Indo-European language family is merely the top of an iceberg (Gray, Russell D. and Quentin D. Atkinson 2003, Language-tree divergence times support the Anatolian theory of Indo-European origin. *Nature* 426: 435–439). Many of the criticisms of the phylogenetic approach apply to all or most of the papers which deal with the topic, although some are specific to the single article that commands our attention. In general terms, the critique focuses on "Mapping the Origins" for three reasons: it represents the pinnacle of the research program in question, it has received the most attention in the public media, and the Indo-European language family is particularly important and has an especially problematic intellectual history, as discussed in *The Indo-European Controversy* (Asya 2015.57).

14. As J.P. Mallory observed, there is only one route to the reconstruction of Indo-European culture that offers any hope of reliability and that is language. Although we might compare cultural traditions, behaviour, or material culture among the different Indo-European groups, this exercise would be a very uncertain plunge into comparative ethnography or archaeology and we would be forced to compare peoples at vastly different time depths. (Mallory 2006.106) Yet, many archaeologists, accustomed to digging up real things, have a low opinion of those who merely reconstruct hypothetical phonemes, so called "linguistic prehistory." (Anthony 2007.21). However, I consider that a well-defined cultural element cannot suddenly appear in different time periods and territories without a human contact. Next, I highlight parts of the mentioned text and their correspondence on the subject in question, bypassing the mythological trap.

Time

14. The fundamental question concerning the concrete existence of a protolanguage is its location in space and time. Thus for Proto-Indo-European the fundamental question in this area is the

chronology and territory of the protolanguage whose breakup led to the formation of the historical daughter dialects (Gamkrelidze 1995.757). The chronology of Proto-Indo-European in the light of evidence concerning the Anatolian linguistic system from the earliest Anatolian onomastics and hydronymics disclose constructions hydronyms which are compounds with a second element *-ḥapa-* (cf. Hitt. *ḥapa-* 'river') e.g. (id. 759) In the light of evidence concerning the breakup of the Greek-Armenian-Aryan dialect grouping, the Mycenaean Greek and its position as a dialect, The Proto-Indo-European as a linguistic community is datable to the fifth to fourth millennia BC (id. 761). In another opinion, for the invention of the wheel, and consequently of wheeled vehicles, the evidence points away from Anatolia and later than 6500 BC, and 3500 BC does seem to be in the right time frame (Asya 2015.177). In our text, at the first Critias asks for "leniency given the immensity of the topics" (Plato 2008.103) showing that "our words are never going to be more than images" (id. 104). He points out the difficulty of discussing historical events, given the critical expectations of the public, and asks for the help of the goddess Memory, for those that happened 9000 years ago, issues that he wishes to remind (id. 105). The time elapsed from a certain historical event, could not be calculated by the ancient Greeks, who did not have the necessary technical methods. An interesting element here would be considerable time elapsed from an event, because we have no element to give credibility to those indicated in the text. This dating can only speculatively establish the topic of discussion as the Proto-Indo-European period, as the most important event that happened thousands of years ago.

The land of the blest

Our life, our health and sickness, are bound up with what we eat and drink. The gods are nourished by special aliments. That they do not eat or drink human food is stated explicitly in Greek and Indian texts. (West 2007.158) Greek parallels spring to mind at once: the virtuous Hyperboreans who live beyond the North Wind, and the White Island in the Black Sea to which in the epic *Aethiopis* Achilles was translated after his death in battle at the hands of Apollo and Alexander. (id.349). An Irish legend the Land of the Living, remembers one country where there is neither sickness nor age nor death; where happiness lasts forever and there is no satiety; where food and drink do not diminish when consumed; where to wish for something is to possess it; where a hundred years are as one day. (id. 350)

In our text, Poseidon, as a god, easily organized the central island. Once he had fetched up two underground springs — one warm, the other flowing cold from its source — and caused all kinds of food to grow in sufficient quantities from the soil, he fathered and reared five pairs of twin sons. (Plato 2008.112). Their empire brought them many goods from abroad, but the island by itself provided e them with most of the necessities of life. In the first place, they had everything, solid or fusible, that could be mined from the ground, and in fact in many parts of the island there was dug

up from the ground something which is now no more than a name, although in those days it was an actual fact and was second in value only to gold — orichalc (Copper alloy - bronze, Plato 2008.notes to pages 111–15). Second, woodland produced plenty of every kind of timber that builders might need for their labours, and bore enough food for both wild and domesticated animals. (id.113). There were in the mountains many wealthy villages with their rural populations; rivers, lakes, and meadows kept every species of tame and wild creature adequately supplied with food; and there was plenty of timber, of various types, which was more than sufficient for any kind of task and for every occasion (id.117).

Divine twins

16. Although it does not exist convincing lexical set for these ‘sons of the sky god’, they are abundantly represented at every level in myth, history and folklore in the various Indo-European traditions (Mallory 2006.432). An Indian hymn is addressed to the two Asvins, the divine twins whose equation with the Greek Dioskouroi 'Zeus's boys' Castor and Pollux is one of the surer comparisons in Indo-European mythology (Watkins 1995.114). We have sufficient grounds for belief in a pair of divine twins, Indo-European specific, who rode horses through the sky and rescued men from mortal peril in battle. If it be asked what sea the worshippers of these prehistoric divinities went down to in *nāwes and sailed on and foundered in, the likely answer is the northern Black Sea or the Sea of Azov (West 2007.191, 483). Twins are correlated with atmospheric disorder is something very commonly accepted throughout the world, including Canada. In America, twins were endowed with special powers to bring good weather, to dispel storms, and the like (Lévi-Strauss 1978.11). However, only for Indo-Europeans sacrifice serves as the foundation myth. Here we find two beings, twins, one known as ‘Man’ and his ‘Twin’ with a possible Latin cognate Remus, the brother of Romulus. In this myth ‘Man’, the ancestor of humankind, sacrifices his ‘Twin’. The two myths, creation and foundation of a people, find a lexical overlap in the Norse myth where the giant Ymir is cognate with Skt Yama and also means ‘Twin’ (Mallory 2006.435). In our text, the same function of the twins is present, the foundation of the world and the sacrifice of one. The God (Poseidon) gave the firstborn of the eldest twins his mother’s home and the plot of land around it, which was larger and more fertile than anywhere else, and made him king of all his brothers, while giving each of the others many subjects and plenty of land to rule over. (Plato 2008.112). All over the world, twins are correlated with different phenomena, but specifically Indo-European, it is the myth of the founding of the world by twins, as it appears in our text.

Social functions

17. Indo-European society was stratified. According to Dumézil three social functions tended to determine social stratification:

a) The first function was concerned with the maintenance of magico-religious and juridical order

(‘L’administration a la fois mysterieuse et reguliere du monde!)

b) The second function was related to physical prowess (‘Le jeu de la vigueur physique, de la force principalement, mais non uniquement guerriere!)

c) The third function was the provision of sustenance, the maintenance of physical well-being, plant and animal fertility, and other related activities. (‘La fecondite avec beaucoup de consequences et resonances, telles que la prosperity la sante la longue vie, la tranquillite, la volupte, le “nombre” . ’) (Littleton 1973: 4-5; Dumézil 1952: 7). Priests, warriors, and miners, farmers or herdsmen, these three functions constitute the tripartition of Indo-European society for Dumézil. (Oosten 2015:18) (Mallory 2006.438). Plato observe that ”In those days, most of the inhabitants of this land — most classes of citizens — were occupied with the crafts and with agriculture, but the warrior class, which from the very beginning had been separated off by godlike men, lived apart.” (Plato 208.107). Then, the warriors, lived all by themselves around the temple, and had also enclosed the heights within a single wall, like the garden of a single house (id. 110). Further, the good organization and the components of the army are discussed (id. 119,120). All this points to a social stratification on three levels (farmers, priests, warriors).

Final battle

18. Indo-European cultures reveal traces of an Indo-European eschatological myth, a myth that describes the end of the world in terms of a cataclysmic battle. The end comes in the form of a major battle in which gods, demi-gods, or major heroes, are slain (Mallory 2006.439). The two sides then prepare for a major war and the two forces come together and annihilate each other in a cataclysmic battle, and the myth may not be just eschatological but rather represent a mythic encounter that brought a past golden age to an end (id. 440). This is also the situation in Atlantis, where the final battle takes place that led to the end of the old era. The battle went on between those on both sides of Hercules' Columns. (Plato 2008.105) The war next to the flood led to the disappearance of the old civilization. Although it seems the dialogue is not over, he has reached the final conclusion. Plato recalls in the background of the story, about the great war declared between those who lived between the Pillars of Heracle and the barbarians from the outside (Plato 2008.105). He states that this war was a global one and suggests that he led to the end of the known world. (Id.) It is interesting here to observe the global change that takes place after the great battle. Thus Plato shows that this great war "that one side was led right through to the end of the fighting by Athens, while the other side was commanded by the kings of Atlantis (id. 105), and this war "reveal details of the many non-Greek peoples and all the Greek communities that existed then" (id. 106). The parallel is actually made between these "Greek communities" who were represented by atlases and "many non-Greek peoples" who are suggested to be the old barbarians. The Great War brought about a major change, which led to the dispersion of what was called "Greek communities",

and in the end Athens of Plato became a Greek people.

The Flood. The end of Old Europe

19. Around 4200–4100 BCE the climate began to shift, and solar insolation decreased, glaciers advanced in the Alps, and winters became much colder. Variations in temperature in the northern hemisphere are recorded in the annual growth rings in oaks preserved in bogs in Germany and in annual ice layers in the GISP2 glacial ice core from Greenland. According to these sources, extremely cold years happened first in 4120 and 4040 BCE. They were harbingers of a 140-year-long, bitterly cold period lasting from 3960 to 3821 BC, with temperatures colder than at any time in the previous two thousand years. Investigations in the lower Danube valley showed that floods occurred more frequently and erosion degraded the riverine floodplains where crops were grown. Agriculture in the lower Danube valley shifted to more cold-tolerant rye in some settlements. Quickly these and perhaps other stresses accumulated to create an enormous crisis. (Antony 2007.227), which led to important changes on the map of ancient Europe. In our text, such changes of climate are retained and the many devastating floods are remembered in the interval of 9,000 passed (Plato 2008.108).

The King and the Virgin

21. A recurrent theme, though not without considerable modifications or differences, is that of a virgin rescuing a king. The basic structure involves a king whose future including his descendants is endangered because of his immediate male relatives but is allowed to prevail because of a virgin who provides the offspring necessary to the king's survival. In Roman tradition King Numitor's line is ensured by the birth of Romulus and Remus because his virgin daughter, Rhea Silvia, was made pregnant by Mārs (Marolly 2006.437). In our myth, the king is replaced by the primordial god and the descendants are not insured by a virgin, but by a mortal. God (Poseidon) gained the island of Atlantis as his province, and he settled there the children borne for him by a mortal woman in a certain part of the island (Plato 2008.111).

Homeland

22. Recently, some scholars claim to have found “decisive support” for Indo-European origins among Neolithic farmers in central Anatolia some 8,000 to 9,500 years ago by using techniques of phylogenetic and phylogeographical analysis designed, respectively, to construct evolutionary family trees and trace the spread of viruses. They claim to have overturned the prevailing hypothesis, which holds instead that the language family emerged among pastoral peoples living in the grasslands, or steppes, north of the Black Sea some 4,000 to 6,000 years ago. According to a recent Science study, an Indo-European homeland in Anatolia should now be considered closer to the truth than one in the steppe area. (Asya 2015.2) It might seem odd that this seemingly obscure topic would have attracted such intense media attention. But the Indo-European question, with its

long, complex, and vexed heritage, is more intellectually significant than it might appear at first glance. No other language family comes close to the global significance of Indo-European, which encompasses the mother tongues spoken by almost half of humankind. Scientific progress does not always guarantee the discovery of the truth, nor do advanced mathematical approaches always produce accurate results (id.). Returning to the text in question, here is often insisted that the homeland is the place where the ancestors of the Greeks left. The origin of the first Greek speakers, may be a relevant element in identifying the proto-Indo-European Homeland.

IV. Possible research directions

23. Even if the text is so far from the scientific rigor of today, the relevant cultural elements that are included, point to a much earlier discovery - 360 B.C. of three social functions, for example, or confirm many others contemporary discoveries about the ancient civilization. The proper names used for people or for different geographical elements, do not have a correspondent at present, and in our text they may be mere imagined elements. That is why I have not tried to speculate on their identification at present, with a small exception below. Moreover, I did not try to include in the article all the relevant elements of the text, a matter that could be the subject of a later work.

24. But I dare to formulate the hypothesis that the origin of the first Greek speakers, as shown in the text, may be a relevant element in identifying the proto-Indo-European Homeland. It be widely accepted that Greek-speakers were preceded in Greece by speakers of an Indo-European language of the Anatolian type, similar to Luwian. The first speakers of Greek, or rather of the language that was to develop into Greek, I will call them mello-Greeks, arrived in Greece, on the most widely accepted view, at the beginning of Early Helladic III, that is, around 2300 BC. They came by way of Epirus, probably from somewhere north of the Danube. Recent writers have derived them from Romania or eastern Hungary (West 2007.8).

24. Then, in most cases we are probably speaking of language shift between neighbouring peoples, there is no requirement whatsoever that the trail of language shift should also leave a clearly defined genetic trail as well. (Mallory 2006.451) The population that used proto-language is radically altered, even if the linguistic traces point to the same place. Plato even remembers that those who survived on each occasion were illiterate mountain-dwellers, who had heard only the names of the rulers of the land and knew hardly anything about their achievements (Plato 2008.107). Then, in Plato's day some of mountains in the area sustain only bees, but not long ago trees from there were cut as roof-timbers for very substantial buildings, and the roofs are still sound (id. 109).

25. The borders that mark on an imaginary map of language the spread of Indo-European isoglosses, have a common point, which reaches part of what is today the common territory of

Transylvania, Hungary, Croatia and Serbia, bordered by the Carpathians, the Austrian Alps and the Dinaric Alps. (I Remains) The same area is a point of reference for the archaeological discoveries of what is called the Bronze Age. However, without a commonly agreed phylogeny, an essential key cannot be obtained for evaluating competing hypotheses (Mallory 2013.148), and this phylogeny seems to be impossible to reconstruct for the past, given the population movements over time.

26. The "curious" Romanian language in its basic dialect It is also an element that can must be studied. Then I noticed that, in the Black Sea area, the Romanian language is somewhat in contrast to everything that is spoken around it (Hungarian, Serbian, Russian, Bulgarian, Turkish, etc.). The old Romanian dialects are homogeneous and mutually intelligible in a high degree, therefore they do not fit in a scenario, which establishes that the present language descends from the Latin language spoken in Dacia before 270 EN. The surprising uniformity of the old Romanian dialects indicates that the Romanian language does not descend from the Latin spoken once in Dacia and therefore the date when Dacia ceased to be a part of the Roman Empire is irrelevant for dating the appearance of the Romanian language (Asya 2015 102). If the Romanian descended from the Latin spoken in Roman Dacia, prior to the date of 270 EN, it should have spread later in areas that were not part of the conquered territory. If this had happened, it would be expected to find a greater dialect differentiation from the "old Romanian territories" of Roman Dacia, compared to the areas where the language arrived later. A parallel can be made here, for example, with the great dialect differentiation in the basic countries of Russia (the European part), compared with the territories acquired more recently such as (Siberia or the Far East) (id. 103).

27. If the Romanian language did not appear in part of the territory of Romania, no other place could be found to justify such a population movement, which would then cover the entire territory of the country today, including the Republic of Moldova. Therefore, most likely, the Romanian was formed in an area that includes the present territory of the country. But if so, then how is it justified by its basic resemblance to Latin, probably the most developed language in Europe of that period (270 EN) and beyond this similarity borrowed from the neighboring languages spoken in the vicinity, and especially the common lexicon with the Hungarian language? Is this merely a result of cultural closures and exchanges, or, if I may say so, a dissolution of a "primordial" language in the immediate vicinity and much more than that (Ulici 2016)?

28. Another important aspect, is the supposed disappearance of the Dacian language, an Indo-European language attested by Herodotus and Tucidides somewhere in an area that also includes the present territory of Romania, which would not have left any relevant traces (Mallory 1997.145), of course if these traces would not even be considered the basic vocabulary of the Romanian language. Thus, as we can see, a simple chronological marking "270 EN" for separating the Eastern Romanic

languages from the other members of the language family, based on the historical event of the Roman withdrawal from Dacia, is misleading and does not say anything about the real history of the Romanian language. Moreover, as far as historical linguistics is concerned, the date is arbitrary (Asya 2015.104).

29. Have not been investigated at all the linguistic elements of the Romanian language, especially those with unknown etymology, or the exact correspondences, of some linguistic terms, for example, between the Romanian and the usual English languages (Ulici 2017 vol I and vol II).

30. The Romanian Academy makes a list of the 115 sure native words in 2006 (Mihăilă 2006). According to the Explanatory Dictionary of the Romanian language that contains in the official edition a number of 66,979 definitions, these native words represent 0.171 of the vocabulary mass.

31. The position of most linguistic anthropologists today is that the most fully accept the existence of both diversity and universality across languages and cultures, and any proposed universals must be shown to be truly universal and not just the result of inappropriate generalizations stemming from Western cultural or linguistic categories (Aheam 2012.69). In this hypothesis, it should be noted that the Roman language, throughout its known history, is not observed to have transmitted, but only to have received linguistically. If is so, this language must have been highly diversified by region, depending on the area of influence, and it could not be so unitary. The unity of the Romanian language in its basic form, indicates a possible previous appearance.

32. The territory of the homeland does not appear to have been an island, even though it is specifically so called. A fairly large territory but not very wide which allowed good communication along. The elements point to the indicated area within the Carpathian Mountains, the Austrian Alps and the Dinaric Alps.

33. Commercial relations between eastern central Europe (the middle and lower Danube area) continued from Neolithic times into the first centuries of the second millennium BC. The Pecica people (or Periam - Romania) in the lower Tisza basin were the chief transmitters of the Near Eastern metal forms to the north. Oriental metal objects were obtained through intertribal exchange. Gradually these spread to the whole Danube basin: to the Nagyrev group on the middle Danube south of Budapest, to the Kisapostag group in western Hungary, and ultimately to their northern neighbors. The trade routes probably were about the same as during the Neolithic and Chalcolithic times: central Balkan Morava and Yardar (Axios) rivers, the Aegean Sea, the western and southern coasts of Asia Minor leading to Cilicia, Cyprus, Syria, and Palestine (Gimbutas 1965.32).

34. If the Greeks had come from somewhere north of the Danube, then I would try to identify a geographical landmark in Plato's myth. This is also the only landmark in the text in question, on which I speculate here. I notice that, the Iron Gates region of Serbia and Romania, also known as the Danube Gorge, is the place where the Danube enters through a gorge in the Carpathian

mountains, run to the Black Sea. Numerous whirlwinds choke the waters of the Danube. Prehistoric peoples chose this enigmatic area to erect shrines dedicated to the ultimate mystery: the regeneration of life from death. The first and largest site explored in the area is Lepenski Vir, dating from 6500-5500 BC, but many other similar sites have been found along the Danube between Romania and Serbia. (Gimbutas 1999.23-24%). The location and the corroboration with the other data can lead to the working hypothesis that the Iron Gate area is the place called by the ancient Greeks "Pillars of Heracles".

35. If we were to refer only to language and considering that it is obviously evolutionary, I must point out that a complete disappearance of the so-called proto-language does not seem possible. He could not be replaced for the most part, or could not receive a new form on unrecognizable one. This supposed lexical repopulation of the basic formation area does not seem to be a indelible conception. There must be an area where the proto-language is still preserved as a unitary lexical corpus and this may be the area indicated by me, with the specifications shown above.

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